

Design and Implementation of L1 Cache in VexRiscv Processor

Smitha N ¹, Basavaraj M ¹, Amith B ¹, and Chethan M S ¹

¹*Dept. of ECE RNS Institute of Technology Bengaluru, India , smithanesara81@gmail.com, basavarajmanegar04@gmail.com, amithb071104@gmail.com, chethanms652@gmail.com*

Abstract

VexRiscv is a configurable RISC-V soft-core processor written in SpinalHDL and widely used in FPGA-based embedded and real-time systems. In its minimal configuration, the core typically operates without an integrated cache, which leads to high memory access latency and reduced instruction throughput for memory-intensive workloads. This work presents the design, integration, and evaluation of a 4 KB direct mapped L1 cache for the VexRiscv processor. The cache is implemented using on-chip Block RAM and tightly coupled to the processor's instruction and data interfaces. Functional verification and performance analysis are carried out using a RISC-V toolchain and Verilator-based cycle-accurate simulation. Experimental results demonstrate a 63.2% reduction in total cycle count and a 54.9% reduction in executed instructions for a benchmark application, while preserving functional correctness. The proposed architecture shows that even a compact, low complexity cache can substantially improve the performance of FPGA-resident RISC-V soft cores without major modifications to the underlying microarchitecture.

Keywords: VexRiscv, RISC-V, L1 Cache, FPGA, Spinal HDL, Verilator, Performance Optimization

1 Introduction

The RISC-V instruction set architecture (ISA) has emerged as a prominent open standard due to its modularity, extensibility, and ecosystem support. Its openness enables designers to explore novel architectural optimizations and customize processor microarchitectures for domain-specific applications. VexRiscv is a soft-core implementation of the RISC-V ISA written in SpinalHDL, designed to be highly configurable in terms of pipeline depth, memory hierarchy, and optional units such as MMUs and caches. This flexibility makes VexRiscv

a popular choice for FPGA-based system-on-chip (SoC) proto types and educational platforms. However, the minimal configuration of VexRiscv often omits cache memory to reduce resource usage and design complexity. While this configuration is sufficient for simple control-oriented tasks, it becomes a bottleneck for memory bound and computation-intensive workloads, where repeated accesses to off-core memory significantly increase execution time. In such scenarios, the absence of an on-chip cache leads to frequent stalls, higher average memory access time, and degraded overall performance. To address these limitations, this work focuses on the design and integration of a lightweight L1 cache subsystem for the VexRiscv processor. The principal objective is to reduce effective memory latency and improve instruction throughput with minimal hardware overhead. A 4 KB direct-mapped cache implemented using FPGA Block RAM is integrated into the memory interface of VexRiscv. The impact of the proposed cache is evaluated using a benchmark program compiled with the RISC-V GNU toolchain and simulated using Verilator. The contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- Design of a compact L1 cache architecture suitable for FPGA-based VexRiscv cores.
- Seamless integration of the cache into the VexRiscv memory interface with support for hit/miss detection and replacement.
- Quantitative performance analysis showing significant reduction in cycle count and instruction count while preserving correctness.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents a literature survey of recent cache-related research on RISC-V-based systems. Section III describes the overall methodology adopted for cache design and evaluation. Section IV explains the implementation details of the cache architecture and its integration with VexRiscv. Section V discusses the simulation results and performance improvements. Section VI outlines the future scope, and Section VII concludes the paper.

2 Literature Review

Extensive research has been conducted to enhance the memory subsystem and cache efficiency of RISC-V-based processors, with particular emphasis on performance, scalability, and power efficiency. A Data Filter Cache (DFC) mechanism is proposed in [1] to minimize redundant memory accesses in the VexRiscv core, thereby reducing access latency and power consumption. While the approach improves cache hit rates, the authors observe that pipeline integration introduces timing challenges during cache line fill operations, which may limit the maximum achievable operating frequency. This work highlights the importance of pipeline-aware cache design. ARCANE [2] redefines the role of the last-level cache by transforming it into a near-memory compute accelerator capable of executing vector operations. By enabling computation within the cache, ARCANE significantly reduces data movement overhead and achieves performance improvements ranging from $30\times$ to $84\times$ on convolutional

neural network workloads using 8-bit precision. The design maintains software compatibility through a software-defined ISA, demonstrating the feasibility of cache structures serving dual roles as both storage and compute units. A waveform-driven methodology for cache performance evaluation is presented in [3]. Instead of embedding hardware counters or modifying HDL descriptions, the authors utilize Waveform Analysis Language (WAL) scripts to extract key metrics such as cache hit rate, latency, and throughput directly from simulation waveforms. This approach improves design reuse and enables architecture-independent cache analysis across different stages of development. In [4], a high-performance instruction cache (HPIC) is introduced for RISC-V many-core processors. The cache incorporates a four-stage pipeline along with an integrated prefetch engine to enhance instruction delivery efficiency. Implemented in 7 nm technology, the design achieves a peak operating frequency of 2.3 GHz with a two-cycle hit latency and delivers an average performance improvement of approximately $1.06\times$ on large-scale workloads, while remaining compatible with the OpenPiton framework. A programmable L1 cache architecture with dynamic external memory coverage is proposed in [5]. By allowing runtime adjustment of address mapping, the cache effectively reduces DDR memory traffic and improves memory utilization without disrupting conventional cache hierarchies. This work demonstrates the advantages of flexible address-space management at the cache level. The integration and verification of a 32 KB, four-way set associative, write-through L1 data cache within the SweRV EH1 RISC-V core is discussed in [6]. The cache employs an LRU replacement policy and is verified using Verilator based simulation. Experimental results indicate improved data throughput and reduced memory access latency while maintaining functional correctness. A context cache architecture for multicore RISC-V processors is presented in [7]. By storing and reusing context related information, the proposed mechanism significantly reduces context-switch overhead. The authors report up to a 99% reduction in context-switch latency, leading to improved responsiveness in real-time and multi-threaded systems. Seamless cache extension for FPGA-based multicore RISC-V systems-on-chip is explored in [8]. The proposed design integrates a scalable data cache subsystem with hardware supported cache coherence, achieving hit rates exceeding 90% with minimal area overhead. The architecture eliminates software-level coherence management, thereby simplifying programming and improving shared-memory performance. Cache optimization techniques targeting harsh operating environments are investigated in [9]. The authors propose a robust direct-mapped data cache designed to operate reliably under extreme temperature and pressure conditions. The cache achieves a hit rate of approximately 97% and maintains stable operation at frequencies up to 180 MHz, emphasizing the importance of resilient cache designs for rugged applications. A two-dimensional reconfigurable cache architecture is introduced in [10], enabling dynamic adjustment of both cache size and associativity based on workload requirements. Implemented on FPGA platforms, the design demonstrates improved energy efficiency and processing performance compared to fixed-configuration caches. In [11], an open-source high-performance data cache (HPD cache) is integrated with the CVA6 RISC-V core. The flexible L1 data cache design achieves up to a 234% performance improvement with only a 5.9% increase in area, underscoring the benefits of scalable, open-source cache architectures for high-performance RISC-V sys-

tems. Finally, [12] examines the impact of cache organization on microarchitectural security by comparing VIPT (Virtually Indexed Physically Tagged) and PIPT (Physically Indexed Physically Tagged) cache designs. The study demonstrates that cache architecture significantly affects both performance and vulnerability to side-channel attacks such as Spectre, highlighting the necessity of incorporating security considerations into cache hierarchy design.

3 Methodology

Figure 1: Block diagram of the proposed cache memory subsystem integrated with VexRiscv.

Figure 1 illustrates the internal organization of the proposed cache subsystem. The VexRiscv CPU issues address and control signals for load and store operations, which are first processed by a size controller and way controller that determine how each request is mapped into the cache. The tag memory stores address tags and associated valid bits, while the data memory holds the corresponding cache lines, implemented using FPGA Block RAM resources. A central Finite State Machine (FSM) orchestrates all cache operations, including handling read and write requests, determining cache hits or misses, and initiating block fetches from main memory. For every incoming memory request, the FSM compares the tag extracted from the CPU address with the stored tag in the selected cache line. If a valid match is found (cache hit), the GMUX unit routes the appropriate data word from the data memory back to the CPU. If no match is found (cache miss), the FSM triggers a memory access to fetch the required block, updates the tag and data memories, and then supplies the requested data to the CPU. When multiple potential candidates exist for replacement (in a more associative design), the Least Recently Used (LRU) controller unit would determine which cache line to evict based on recent access history. In the present work, a direct-mapped organization is adopted to minimize hardware complexity; however, the control structure is designed such that more advanced replacement strategies could be integrated in future extensions.

3.1 Mishandling Mechanism

The miss-handling mechanism is crucial for ensuring correct and efficient operation. When a miss is detected, the FSM moves the cache into a refill state. During this period, the

CPU pipeline is temporarily stalled, and the current program counter value is effectively frozen to prevent the execution of invalid instructions. A block read is then issued to main memory, and the returned data is written into the appropriate data memory entry while the corresponding tag and valid bits are updated. Once the refill is complete, the FSM resumes normal operation, and the CPU continues execution using the freshly loaded data. This mechanism ensures that the cache remains transparent to software while significantly reducing average memory access time for subsequent accesses to the same block.

3.2 Replacement Policy

Although the cache implemented in this work is direct mapped, replacement policy concepts are still relevant when considering future scalability. A Least Recently Used (LRU) replacement strategy is attractive for set-associative caches as it attempts to retain the most frequently accessed blocks in the cache. An LRU controller typically maintains a small amount of state information that reflects recent access patterns and uses this information to select a victim block when a replacement is required. In resource-constrained FPGA environments, simplified or pseudo-LRU mechanisms may be preferred, but the fundamental goal remains the same: maximizing hit rate while keeping hardware overhead low.

4 Implementation

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the methodology adopted in this work follows a systematic sequence of steps. The process begins with software environment initialization, where all required tools such as the RISC-V GNU toolchain, Java, Verilator, and the SpinalHDL framework are installed and configured. Subsequently, the VexRiscv core is obtained and analyzed to identify appropriate insertion points for the cache module within the memory access path. In the next stage, the cache architecture is designed and integrated into the processor. This involves defining cache parameters (such as size, block size, and mapping), designing tag and data storage structures, and developing control logic for hit/miss detection and replacement. The VexRiscv memory interface is then modified so that all instruction and data memory requests are routed through the cache. Once the integration is complete, the simulation and test environment is prepared. Benchmark programs are written in C, compiled using the RISC-V toolchain, and executed on both the baseline (no cache) and cache-enabled configurations using Verilator. During simulation, performance-related signals such as total cycle count, instruction retirement count, and output data are captured and logged. The subsequent step is performance evaluation, where metrics like total execution cycles, number of executed instructions, and correctness of results are compared between the two configurations. Optionally, the architecture may be synthesized on an FPGA platform to obtain realistic area, power, and timing estimates. Finally, the collected data is analyzed to quantify performance gains and identify potential directions for enhancement.

Figure 2: Overall workflow for L1 cache integration and evaluation on VexRiscv.

4.1 Initialize Environment

The initial step consists of setting up the development and simulation environment:

- Install Java, Verilator, and the RISC-V GNU toolchain on the host machine.
- Clone the VexRiscv repository and generate a suitable core configuration using SpinalHDL.
- Verify that the baseline VexRiscv configuration successfully compiles and runs a simple test program.

4.2 Baseline Measurement

Before integrating the cache, baseline measurements are recorded:

- Run the benchmark program on the original VexRiscv core without any cache.
- Capture total cycle count and instruction count using performance counters or simulation logs.
- Validate functional correctness by observing the final program output (SUM value).

4.3 Cache Design and Integration

The cache module is designed and attached to the VexRiscv memory interface:

- Define the cache as a 4 KB direct-mapped L1 block with a fixed block size.
- Implement tag memory, data memory (mapped to FPGA Block RAM), valid bits, and control logic.
- Modify the CPU's instruction and data ports so that all memory requests pass through the cache controller.
- On a cache hit, data is served directly from the cache; on a miss, a memory fetch is initiated and the cache line is updated.

4.4 Simulation and Performance Evaluation

After integration, the design is verified and evaluated:

- Re-run the benchmark on the cache-enabled VexRiscv configuration using Verilator.
- Measure total cycle count and instruction count, and confirm that the program output remains correct.
- Compare all metrics between the baseline and cache enabled configurations to quantify performance improvement.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 RTL Schematic Analysis

Present your findings clearly and objectively. Use figures and tables to illustrate key results. Do not interpret the results in this section; save that for the discussion. Figure 3 represents the internal hardware organization of the VexRisc-V processor, highlighting the major datapath components. The Register File stores RISC-V general-purpose registers used for instruction execution and temporary storage. The ALU block performs arithmetic, logical, and shift operations required by the RISC-V instruction set. The MMU (Memory Management Unit) manages memory addressing, access permissions, and address mapping. A dedicated L1 Cache block is integrated between the MMU and data bus to reduce memory latency and speed up instruction/data access. This cache stores recently accessed data and instructions, minimizing frequent main memory accesses and improving overall performance. The Data Bus provides the communication channel between the processor core, cache, and external memory. Green interconnections represent control and data signals responsible for pipeline execution and transaction flow. Overall, the schematic illustrates how the L1 cache integration enhances VexRisc-V efficiency by enabling faster memory access and optimized processing.

Figure 3: RTL schematic of the VexRiscV processor with integrated 4 KB L1 cache.

5.2 Baseline and Cache-Enabled Metrics

The benchmark considered in this study computes the sum of the first 1000 natural numbers. The same program is executed on both the baseline VexRiscv core (without cache) and the cache-enabled core. For the baseline configuration, the simulation reports a total of 14117 cycles and 10295 retired instructions, and the final SUM value is correct. After enabling the 4 KB L1 cache, the same benchmark completes in 5187 cycles with 4651 retired instructions, while still producing the correct SUM value. These measurements already indicate a substantial gain in performance purely through cache integration.

5.3 Simulation Output Screenshots

```

jmem[0]-1381817c jmem[1]-23268108 jmem[2]-138481f2 jmem[3]-f3278668
VCD info: dumpfile dump.vcd opened for output.
SUM = 499500
CYCLES = 14117
INSTRET = 10295
tb.v:80: $finish called at 108600880 (3ps)
    
```

Figure 4: Verilator simulation output of VexRiscv executing the benchmark without L1 cache.

Figures 4 and 5 show the Verilator console outputs for the executions without and with the proposed L1 cache, respectively. In both cases, the benchmark program computes the same SUM value of 499500, confirming that the functional behavior of the processor remains unchanged after cache integration. The primary difference lies in the reported cycle and instruction counts. The no-cache configuration takes 14117 cycles and executes 10295 instructions, whereas the cache-enabled configuration requires only 5187 cycles and

```
VCD info: dumpfile dump.vcd opened for output.
SUM      =    499588
CYCLES   =    5187
INSTRET  =    4651
test4kb.v:103: $finish called at 100000000 (1ps)
```

Figure 5: Verilator simulation output of VexRiscv executing the benchmark with 4 KB L1 cache.

4651 instructions. The reduction in cycles reflects fewer memory stall events, while the reduction in instructions suggests that pipeline bubbles and repeated wait operations are eliminated when cache hits serve the majority of requests. These observations validate that the performance improvements stem exclusively from optimized memory access behavior rather than any modification of algorithmic complexity.

5.4 Bar Graph Performance Comparison

Figure 6: Comparison of cycle count and instruction count for VexRiscv with and without 4 KB L1 cache.

Fig. 6 presents a bar graph comparing the cycle and instruction counts for the baseline and cache-enabled configurations. The graph clearly illustrates the magnitude of improvement obtained through cache integration. The cycle count drops from 14117 to 5187, corresponding to a reduction of 63.2%, while the instruction count reduces from 10295 to 4651, yielding an improvement of 54.9%. The substantial height difference between the bars visually highlights the reduced execution time and increased efficiency. Because the program output is identical in both cases, the graph confirms that the L1 cache improves performance without compromising correctness. These results emphasize the importance of exploiting spatial and temporal locality using on-chip caches in soft-core processors implemented on FPGAs.

5.5 Quantitative Performance Summary

Table 1: TABLE I PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF VEXRISCV WITH AND WITHOUT L1 CACHE

Metric	No Cache	4KB Cache	Improvement
Cycle Count	14117	5187	63.2%
Instruction Count	10295	4651	54.9%
Functional Output	Correct	Correct	-

As summarized in Table I, the proposed cache design delivers a significant reduction in both execution cycles and retired instructions. The 63.2% decrease in cycle count indicates a substantial reduction in the number of memory stall cycles, while the 54.9% reduction in instruction count reflects a decrease in idle or wait-related instructions. Importantly, the functional output remains identical in both configurations, which confirms that the cache acts as a transparent performance enhancement mechanism. Overall, the quantitative results establish that even a modest 4 KB direct-mapped cache can provide considerable performance gains for VexRiscv executing memory-intensive workloads.

6 Conclusion

This paper has presented the design, integration, and evaluation of a 4 KB direct-mapped L1 cache for the VexRiscv RISC-V soft-core processor. The cache was implemented using FPGA Block RAM and attached to the processor’s memory interface with minimal changes to the existing microarchitecture. Verilator-based simulation of a benchmark program demonstrated a 63.2% reduction in execution cycles and a 54.9% reduction in retired instructions while preserving functional correctness. These results confirm that even a small, lightweight cache can significantly enhance the performance of FPGA-based soft cores, particularly for memory-bound workloads. The methodology and architectural insights discussed in this work can serve as a basis for further exploration of multi level caches, coherence mechanisms, and adaptive policies in RISC-V-based systems. The present work focuses on a single level, direct-mapped L1 cache integrated into a uniprocessor VexRiscv core. There are several avenues for extending this research. First, multi-level cache hierarchies incorporating L2 or victim caches could be explored to further reduce miss penalties and support larger working sets. Second, more advanced replacement policies, such as pseudo-LRU or adaptive policies that respond to runtime behavior, could be evaluated and selectively implemented to balance hit rate and hardware cost.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank Dr. Smitha N, Associate Professor, Department of ECE, RNS Institute of Technology, Bengaluru, for her continuous guidance, encouragement, and support throughout the course of this project

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